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Rethinking Gender and Return: Mapping patterns and gaps in literature on gender and coerced returns

Concept Note

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Abstract

This concept note maps conceptual, methodological, and empirical gaps in the literature on gender and return migration, with a specific focus on state-induced and coerced forms of return, including assisted return and deportation. Drawing on a purposeful literature review of 49 scientific studies published since 2010, the paper systematically examines how gender is conceptualized, operationalized, and mobilized across different strands of research. Using a structured analytical grid, the review assesses regional and thematic foci, methodological approaches, reflected perspectives, phases of return, and underlying gender frameworks.

The findings reveal pronounced fragmentation in the literature. Research on assisted return and reintegration often relies on place-based and binary understandings of gender, emphasizing culturally rooted constraints and individual-level outcomes, particularly for women. In contrast, the studies on bordering, detention, and return governance conceptualize gender as enacted and ascribed within racialized and gendered regimes of mobility control, offering more nuanced insights into power relations but rarely extending into post-return analysis. Across both strands, significant gaps persist, including limited empirical research on return enforcement practices, a lack of longitudinal and comparative studies, underdeveloped intersectional analyses, and the dominance of receiving-state perspectives. Quantitative and gender-responsive data remain scarce, while reflexivity regarding researcher positionality is seldom addressed.

The paper argues that these gaps reflect deeper tensions between migration management objectives and gender-responsiveness in return governance. It concludes by calling for integrated, intersectional, and reflexive research designs that link enforcement, return, and reintegration processes, and that more systematically account for care relations, agency, and structural inequalities.

Keywords:

Gender, intersectionality, coerced return, research gaps

1. Introduction

This concept note maps conceptual, methodological and evidence gaps in the literature on gender and return, with a focus on state-induced (Koch 2014) or coerced (Şahin-Mencütek & Triandafyllidou 2024) returns (i.e. mainly assisted returns and deportations). The role of gender(s) receives growing attention in research on return migration (King & Lulle 2022) as well as in the governance and management of migration (Mahon 2020). The findings are not always straightforward, and the data contain contradictions, blind spots, and unequal consideration of geopolitically situated perspectives. Forced returns, for example, have been linked to experiences of “failed masculinities”, as they compromise men’s ability to perform roles as migrants and breadwinners (King & Lulle 2022). At the same time, deported male migrants explicitly challenge not only the stigma of deportation but also such notions of “emasculination” (Strijbosch, Mazzucato, & Brunotte 2023) and return aspirations of men have been linked with the explicit desire to re-establish certain notions of masculinity and seek recognition unavailable to them in exile, especially under an uncertain or irregular legal status (Hansen 2008). For women, various sources have identified a greater reluctance to return (King & Lulle 2022; Vlasse 2013) and more pronounced obstacles to ‘reintegration’ compared to men (Hussain, Coskun, & Clevers 2025; International Organization for Migration [IOM] 2023; Sacchetti 2016). Yet, women’s return has also been portrayed as a “transformative process that enhances opportunities for women’s empowerment and agency” (Donato 2023). Complicating such an optimistic picture, polarized images of different gender roles have been found to draw a boundary between (returned) and (non-migrant) women separating them along gendered lines (Dahinden 2010).

To summarise and reflect on the state of research and existing gaps, we conducted a keyword-based literature search across relevant databases, yielding an initial 74 titles on gender and return from various perspectives. These were then filtered, and the 46 remaining titles were analysed using a Kobo-based grid.

2. Methodology

For this research, a purposeful literature review was conducted, drawing on peer-reviewed journal articles, policy reports, and relevant grey literature across various disciplines. Terminology, both on return as well as on gender is quite diverse (Şahin-Mencütek 2024). Thus we identified the following list of keywords as starting point for this literature review: on the one side gender-related terms such as gender, sex, feminism, masculinity, women, male, female, on the other side, terms related to return governance, including return governance, migration management, return and reintegration, assisted return, border control/bordering, migration control, immigration detention, deportation, repatriation, pre-return, pre-departure, deportability. Studies were searched in English. As databases, Google and Google Scholar were selected for their broad accessibility and coverage. As the keywords were entered in English, the search yielded predominantly English-language studies. Suggested articles in other languages were included if considered relevant. To better reflect contemporary sociopolitical conditions, the literature review focused on studies published from 2010 onwards. Publications were included when the abstract clearly indicated a focus on gender in the context of return migration.

There is a considerable and expanding body of literature examining returned migrants as transmitters of gender norms across different places, with mixed findings depending on who returns and from where they return. Included were studies on coerced returns and post-return

reintegration processes, asylum procedures (with a focus on clear links to deportability), as well as immigration detention and other forms of immobilisation and exclusion in the context of (outsourced as well as internal) migration and border controls. Few studies also trace the limited potential for changing gender norms as a result of migration and return (Pinkow-Läpple 2023). Due to time and scope limitations, such literature was excluded from this analysis when the return was entirely self-determined.¹

Limitations: Certain types of return enforcement statistically affect men much more often than women, for example, detention in removal centres and deportation. While this is relevant from a gender perspective, some of the literature treats men as the norm in these contexts (Wissink 2021), with the implication that our keyword-based search yielded more texts on women and diverse genders. Research with a gender-blind view on coerced returns (more likely to cover men's experiences) is therefore less reflected in our sample, which is a limitation of the methodology. Also, large-scale surveys on refugees' return aspirations, which are usually disaggregated by sex, did not appear in the search results.

This body of texts was then analysed using a grid of 13 criteria (using Kobo Toolbox software), aiming to cluster the literature and identify patterns regarding regional foci, reflected perspectives, return phases covered, and conceptualisations of gender. Concretely, we applied basic criteria such as the type of research, type of publication, level of data disaggregation, regional focus, perspective represented and phase, as well as the kind of return and of returnees covered in the publication. In addition to that, we analysed the conceptualization of gender. At a basic level, we asked whether gender was understood in binary or more diverse terms and whether the analysis included one, two or more gender categories. We also listed eight different, somewhat ideal-typical understandings of gender reflecting different disciplinary approaches and strands of literature. These are, of course, not mutually exclusive (and were applied like most other criteria in a multiple-choice way) but selected to refine our analysis of whether and how notions of gender are defined and conceptualized in the literature. The following presentation of findings is structured, distinguishing between gaps identified in the literature and those that have been found to exist in the literature.

3. Findings

3.1 Gaps in the scholarly literature

Gender Gap

The analysis of the literature reveals two basic differences in how notions of gender are understood and used. The first one relates to localisations of gender, either in certain places, societies and communities or in practices, interactions and structures. The second difference, somewhat building on the first, refers to the use of gender either as sets of relatively stable constructs (conflating gender and sex to some extent) or as being enacted, claimed or leveraged in practices, interactions and contestations about return. We find that occurrences of these different uses in the literature are structured. Literature on reintegration after 'assisted returns' (often grey literature) and on self-decided returns tends to apply place-based understandings of gender, where gender norms differ between countries, societies, and sometimes communities. Returning migrants either reluctantly re-adapt to socially and culturally

¹ Other studies that were excluded were dealing, for example, with reintegration in the context of Disarmament, Demobilisation & Reintegration, which concerns armed groups.

loaded norms, constraints and expectations or import and reproduce “alien” gender norms from elsewhere with varying success. Literature on bordering and return governance in contrast unveils the omnipresence and flexibility of gendered perceptions applied to exclude, to legitimize violence and to disregard people’s agency towards their own safety and self-determination. Bordering and migration management studies also tend to focus more on how, why and by whom gender is ascribed, enacted, accomplished and to what effect. This allows for more nuanced analysis of when and how individuals are positioned within racialized and gendered social categories and reveals more about the intricate and paradoxical intersections between social categories such as gender or race and the production of (im)mobility (Sampaio 2014; Wissink 2021).

Thirdly, we clustered the sampled literature along several somewhat ideal-typical (and not mutually exclusive) conceptualizations of gender that we distilled from the literature, corresponding to different ways and contexts of attributing relevance to gender as category of analysis that we hoped would also reveal patterns and gaps. This analysis shows that conceptualizations of gender as a social construction, expressed mainly in ideas about social roles, were by far the most prevalent (45% of the sources). Gender as a protection category (referring to discussions about access to effective protection and rights as well as protection from violence and discrimination) and intersectional understandings (including race, class, sexuality, and legal status) are second with equal proportions. Gender as part of individual identity constructions (identity conflicts and questions of agency and coping) and gender as a culturally situated system of symbols and meanings are reflected in 28 and 21% of the sources, respectively. This renders the categories dealing with structural inequalities (relating to labour and care economics), with access to resources such as income and with gendered power relations (within institutions and as a category of governance) as the least discussed (24%, 17% and again 17% respectively).

Return enforcement and reintegration assistance gap

Resembling trends in coerced return studies more broadly, return enforcement practices are rarely reflected in the literature on gender and returns due to limited accessibility. Few studies draw on empirical research inside detention facilities (Gerlach 2018; Rabin 2009) and foreigners offices (Wissink 2021), while gendered practices of bordering and deportation are partly inferred from interview data (Belknap 2016; Ratia & Notermans 2012). Also – while gendered return decision-making has been studied in contexts of self-decided returns, there is very little on the role of gender in decision-making for or against assisted returns. In fact, the main source for this topic is an early study commissioned by the UK Home Office (Black et al. 2004) which is referenced by some of the later publications (Encinas 2016; Lochan 2017) without adding new data. According to this, many women do not decide for assisted return on their own, but are more susceptible than men to the financial and social pressures applied (Black et al. 2004), leaving Lochan to conclude that “although in theory AVR provides migrant women with greater choice, in practice it often limits their agency” (Lochan 2017).

A growing body of (often grey) literature analyses gendered patterns in ‘reintegration’, often after assisted return (Hussain, Coskun, & Clevers, 2025; IOM, 2023), attributing greater reintegration obstacles for women to lower acquisition of transferable skills and resources, restrictive gender norms and differential network support. Only a few academic studies analyse the design and implementation of AVRR programmes themselves in terms of reinforcing gender inequalities, e.g. through their application of a self-responsibilisation approach that effectively conceals the structural and gendered roots of inequality and precariousness (Paasche

& Skilbrei 2017; Sacchetti 2016). The prevalence and reproduction of gendered hierarchies and power relations in the implementation of reintegration assistance are rarely addressed (Sacchetti 2016; Vollmer & Schmitz-Pranghe 2025), perhaps owing to the perceived benevolence of reintegration assistance compared with other forms of return enforcement.

Data and diversity gap

Most studies are qualitative in nature (74% of the sample), and often quite specific in their regional coverage and thematic focus. Quantitative studies account for less than 5%, with the remaining ones consisting of meta-studies or literature reviews. While there are good reasons why migration data should not only be disaggregated by sex but also become gender-responsive (Szekely 2024), the collection of large-scale, quantitative gender-responsive data is not at all straightforward. The reintegration sustainability survey developed by IOM, for example, allows only binary gender attribution, and data is entered by the enumerator based on presumed sex (IOM 2021). Thinking in terms of intersectionality, the data gap is even more apparent. Hence, there is a general lack of quantitative data and studies on gender and coerced returns. There is also a lack of comparative studies, be it between types of return or between different legislations. Exceptions are a study on gender and economic reintegration in Iraq and Nigeria, which is comparative by design, but not in its findings (Hussain, Coskun, & Clevers 2025) and one by Maastricht University and IOM that analyses impacts of gender and type of return on the sustainability of reintegration, but separately (IOM study 2021).

Thinking in terms of diversity, binary understandings of gender prevail in the literature. In our sample, 63 % of the sources approach gender from a purely binary understanding, with another 21% assuming a somewhat intersectional perspective and 8% mentioning diversity of genders (Fig.1). One study (on reintegration) had attempted to identify respondents of diverse SOGIESC² and failed, attributing this to the risks people may face due to restrictive cultures in the country of origin (without reflecting on their lack of protection before return) (IOM 2023).

Figure 1: Data disaggregation in the reviewed literature according to different conceptualization of gender and topical focus.

² SOGIESC is an acronym encompassing Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity, Gender Expression and Sex Characteristics.

Reflexivity gap

Few studies explicitly discuss researcher positionality and potential impacts or complications on the process of data collection (notable exceptions include Fernández-Sánchez et al. 2023; Gerlach 2018; Ratia & Notermans 2012). We maintain that this is a significant gap, as both gender identities as well as return experiences can be highly sensitive or related to shame or stigma. The perceived appropriateness of articulating specific experiences or aspirations can, in itself, be gendered. Therefore, the process of data collection requires sensitivity, reflexivity and transparency. As Ratia and Notermans reveal, the capability of their interlocutors to openly address different elements of their return experiences was shaped by the situational context (with or without eye contact, while engaged in everyday activities, etc.) (2012). Relevant categories to be considered in such reflections go beyond gender and include at least race and class. A noteworthy but unique example in this regard is a study on transnational Latino families in the US affected by deportations, where data collection was conducted by students with a similar background to the respondents (from immigrant families or immigrants themselves, speaking the same language and experiencing many of the same issues in their own families) (Baker & Marchevsky 2019).

Longitudinal gap

Only one study in the sample took a longitudinal approach to examine the impacts of detention and deportation at the individual level, focusing on the situation of women in a removal centre after their release and after their deportation; however, it did not use the same respondents (Gerlach 2018). Otherwise, studies that focus on gender in the asylum process, during undocumented stay or immigration detention do not expand into the post-return phase, making it harder to understand long-term implications of forced immobilization and return on the lives, safety, mental health or agency of people. A small number of studies have uncovered the ruptures in family and care relations caused by deportations, taking a longitudinal perspective, though (Baker & Marchevsky, 2019; Das Gupta, 2014; Ratia & Notermans, 2012). Studies on reintegration cover the migration histories of respondents to varying degrees but are less likely to include details about encounters with law enforcement (Belknap 2016).

Origin / Receiving society gap

Our analysis also covered whose perspective is most prominently reflected in the literature. It is worth noting that some literature focuses, for example, on returning-country perspectives in a critical manner, thus engaging with but not reproducing said perspectives. With this in mind, the overall breakdown looks as follows (Fig. 2):

Figure 2: The figure shows the actor-perspective categories addressed in the reviewed research papers and the number of papers representing each category.

Assuming that choices regarding the inclusion and exclusion of perspectives and voices in knowledge production have significant ramifications not only for the understanding but also for the accountability of policies, we find that perspectives of the origin countries and non-migrants, family members and communities at the return locations are the least considered. From a geographical angle, most research was embedded in a specific context, looking at migrants coming from a particular region or country of origin, migrating to a specific region/country (Fig. 2). This context-specific research centered especially on South-North movements, looking at South-North migration, mainly focusing on migrants residing in Europe and the migrants from Latin America living in the USA. As King and Lulle (2022) recognized, coerced return among states of the Global South is under-researched. Further, comparative studies among regions or on the supra-regional level remain few.

Figure 3: Distribution of geographical focus in the sample.

Intersectionality gap

Intersectionality is receiving growing recognition as a research perspective on experiences of coerced return (Cleton & Meier, 2023) and as a method for return policy analysis (Fernández-Sánchez et al., 2023). We argue that contradictory findings regarding the meanings and implications of gender in coerced returns partly stem from the disregard for other relevant factors, such as life-cycle stage, care responsibilities, and intersectionality more generally. To give one example, women migrants' experience in the US criminal justice system is strongly mediated by legal status. Whereas non-citizen men are more likely to be penalised than citizens, non-citizen women are less likely to be convicted or incarcerated compared with citizen women, unless they are undocumented (Warner 2025). We therefore encourage the study of gender not in isolation, but by carefully considering its various intersections with age, family status, ethnicity, sexuality, legal status, class, and perhaps other social categories that shape and produce migration and return experiences. Especially the nature and scope of care obligations strongly influence people's (of all genders) mobility decision-making and experiences, while the disruptions in care relations that deportations cause are also less studied (Das Gupta 2014).

4. Patterns and Gaps Identified by the Literature

4.1 Gender-responsive asylum and return governance

Refugee law, such as the 1951 Geneva Convention, was drafted with an androcentric bias (Krause 2024). Calls for making refugee governance more gender-responsive are mainly driven by feminist, women's, and queer perspectives, as they believe that ignoring gender issues worsens risks and inequalities, especially for women (Askola 2010; Hennebry & Petrozziello 2019) and people of diverse genders. Within the EU, research on the intersections between gender and access to protection yields mixed results. Asylum law and practice treat women's protection claims as less severe, especially when relating to rape, domestic violence and forced family planning (Crawley & Lester 2004). While refugee women are often constructed as the "double other" (Spijkerboer 2017), they may also be advantaged in access to protection for other reasons, at least when conforming to heteronormative ideas about womanhood and victimhood (Askola 2010; Spijkerboer 2017). Where this is not the case, asylum systems display increasing levels of "legalized violence" and produce "socially assigned disposability" particularly affecting women and sexual minorities, for example, through mechanisms aimed at establishing and testing credibility of claims based on sexual orientation, exposing lesbian asylum seekers to humiliating and often unsuccessful procedures rendering them deportable (Lewis 2014).

4.2 Gender in the implementation of return and bordering policies

Vulnerability, deservingness

Literature discusses terms that are salient to the implementation of return policies, such as perceived vulnerability and deservingness from a gendered perspective. The conceptualizations of vulnerability, among bureaucrats, NGO staff and migrants, tend to be

gendered female, to the extent that specific vulnerabilities (e.g. of male victims of human trafficking) become invisible and thus much harder to act upon (Paasche & Skilbrei 2017). At the same time, while it is more likely for women to be recognized as victims of trafficking, provision of protection is weak. Legal provisions regarding vulnerability in most receiving states are merely superficial, many real vulnerabilities remain undetected, and even if not, persons may still be detained and returned (Askola 2010). Most drastically, legal pathways for survivors of GBV are systematically undermined by the current mass deportations in the US, where survivors are deported before being able to testify in ongoing trials, exposed to renewed sexualized violence in detention centres or decide to self-deport out of fear, exposing themselves to the risks they tried to escape from (Celorio et al. 2025). Deservingness is constructed even more ambivalently from a gender perspective. While perceptions especially of racialized women range from “crisis-producing threats” to “innocent victims that need saving”, their deservingness (in terms of proving victimhood and deserving protection or assistance seems to depend on them being framed as “victims of their cultures” (Aberman 2022).

Bordering and immobilization

In a broad sense, the ideas of race and gender offer crucial resources for the regulation of mobility. In our mapping of the literature, it is observable that a small number of case studies from various locations discuss how gendered and racialized stereotypes are mobilized for, reinforced through and promoted by policies of bordering. For example, in the case of women crossing the Greece–Turkey border, border police justify their actions and the policies they implement by appealing to cultural stereotypes, which allows them to overlook their suffering (Bosworth, Fili, & Pickering 2018). Women are constructed as “victims of violent patriarchies” happening far away (Aberman 2022), but become viewed as threats to the nation, and even more so to themselves, when they approach or cross a border (Bosworth, Fili, & Pickering 2018). While the border is “a poor site for the identification of victims of trafficking” (Pickering & Ham 2014), women are immobilized under the seemingly benevolent pretext of rescuing them from potential harm, such as trafficking, as (Milivojević 2018) found in her research along the Balkan route. Men, in contrast, are more likely rejected based on racialization and criminalization (ibid.).

These findings about racialization and criminalization during border crossings are echoed by research on the file work in German foreigners (asylum) authorities producing deportable populations. While racializing features of men frequently appear as basis for decision-making, one bureaucrat is quoted saying that “for women there is no distinction in nationality” (Wissink 2021). A more influential aspect in deciding about files of women is that there are significantly fewer spaces in pre-return detention for women (ibid.). One study (Sahraoui 2020) shows that for women, medical humanitarianism at the “humanitarian border” in Melilla (Morocco-Spain border crossing point) generates gendered practices of immobilization and forms of domination produced by care, such as medical assistance for pregnant women and imposed practices of mothering (ibid.): “the entanglement of administrative and medical procedures within border management produces specific constraints for women on the move” (ibid.). Such specific constraints do not exclude women from racialization: “women of particular ages and races, travelling in specific configurations often have a reverse burden of proof to show they are not, or will not be, a victim of trafficking” (Bosworth, Fili, & Pickering 2018; Pickering & Ham 2014).

Illegality, Detention/Removal

Gender and sexuality also play a role in the social constructions of migrant illegality (Lewis 2014). In general, women are more likely to immigrate legally (due to family connections) or to marry out of illegality but less likely to have work permits due to their legal status as dependents. Thus, there are some paradoxical but partly positive effects of immigration law for women, as long as they fulfil heteronormative expectations and their relations of dependency are not abusive (Askola 2010). Pre-removal detention is usually less regulated than regular detention. Formally, the detention is an administrative, not a criminal, proceeding, but factually, conditions and treatment can be more restrictive and less protected (Rabin 2009). Pre-removal detention is increasingly commonplace, not at all confined to being a measure of last resort (Wadia 2015). This implies that more people are arrested upon arrival or at other points before asylum is rejected, and that detention is not limited to a short time frame prior to deportation (ibid). Also, not all detainees are eventually deported (Gerlach 2018), but we have included respective studies. Whereas most people affected by pre-removal detention are men, the number of women and people with diverse SOGIESC among the detained is growing. Research in the US already years ago documented massive overcrowding of the facilities, mixing of detained migrants with convicted criminals, lack of mental health treatment (including for GBV survivors), inadequate or lacking health care including for pregnancies or cervical cancer, separation of mothers from minor children (with US citizenship), extensive use of security measures such as strip search and shackles, and hardly any public oversight, as facilities tend to be run by for-profit companies (Rabin 2009) Research in the UK focused on women's experiences inside removal centres. They were found to experience vilification, lack of autonomy, i.e. are subjected to forced dependence on state institutions or community for survival, and diminishment, a systematic disregard of their needs (Gerlach 2018). This had severe long-term consequences for their mental health and well-being, similar to citizens innocently detained, who often suffer post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) as a result (ibid.).

Another study with female detained non-nationals in Portugal shows that it was long-term vulnerability and precarity that brought many of them into detention. Some had been kicked out by husbands or intimate partners, forced into racialized informal jobs such as sex or domestic work due to lack of legal alternatives (Matos & Esposito 2019). On some occasions, their undocumented status has also been used as a control mechanism by male partners, showing how poor economic conditions and undocumented status reinforce each other in facilitating abuse (ibid.). Also in the US, some women in immigration detention had been reported to ICE by abusive husbands (Rabin, 2009).

Carceral institutions are not only gendered, but they are also cisgendered and cisnormative (describing the norm of a binary gender categorization, where gender is identical with the sex ascribed to a person at birth) (Vogler & Rosales 2023). Research on transwomen in US immigration detention in 2015 showed that while they had the right to openly identify as transwomen and thereby apply for separate accommodation, this did little to ameliorate gendered inequalities. On the contrary, classification as transgender was found to “serve as punishment in itself” and to expose them to gendered forms of punishment and deterrence from seeking legal remedies in addition to suffering denial of hormones, denial of transaffirming medical and mental healthcare, excessive use of solitary confinement or detention with cis men, and searches by men. Judges reportedly held the opinion that they were safe to be returned if they just dressed like men (ibid.).

Deportations have been described as a “gendered racial removal system” (Golash-Boza & Hondagneu-Sotelo, 2013) in the context of the Americas, where men from Mexico and Central America constitute the vast majority of migrants who have been detained and deported since the mid-1990s. Five million people have been deported from the US from 1996 to 2018, the majority of them have close relatives living in the US, and about one quarter have children with US citizenship (Baker & Marchevsky 2019). Some research has studied implications for families and care relations. For the families left behind, the consequences are harsh and gendered. The women often had to give up the apartment and move in with relatives or friends, work several jobs or longer hours to support themselves, their children and the deported partner or husband financially, becoming economically more exploitable (while usually already being restricted to certain poorly paid sectors). Many of the children suffer depression, anxiety and fall behind in school or even have to drop out of education to contribute to family income (Baker & Marchevsky 2019). From a sample of 125 families, a tiny minority of women reported being relieved of an abusive partner, they reported being burdened with additional responsibilities and “becoming the 'protector' for their deported male partner within a complex transnational economic, legal, and affective terrain” (ibid.).

Criminalisation of men for their deportability should not only be studied through the gendered lens of a male ‘breadwinner role’, but it also forcibly restructures care relations (Das Gupta 2014). Migrant practices of fathering and notions of fatherhood are a blind spot, and the literature on gender and return, where the primary focus is on paid, not unpaid labour of migrant men, and criminalisation portrays them as irresponsible (ibid.). The disproportionate targeting of men is both the result and reproduction of an ideology that sees mothers as primary caregivers (ICE has discretion to arrest father and or mother), but detention of mothers has raised a lot more legal and public resistance than detention (under unsafe and dehumanizing conditions) of women without children or men (including fathers) (ibid.). The deportation of the father/husband is not only the loss of one of the family’s breadwinners, but fathers also contribute essentially to care work, as this and other research documents and often continue doing so virtually after deportation (Baker & Marchevsky, 2019). Structural changes in the labor market are observed to be one less studied underlying driver of the crimmigration of men (Golash-Boza & Hondagneu-Sotelo 2013). As the US labor market increasingly relies on service jobs and offers diminishing numbers of construction and manufacturing jobs deems these men disposable and redundant. During the 1990s, the reproductive capacity of Latina immigrant women was constructed as a threat, coinciding with their being more excluded from immigration opportunities and reducing their eligibility for government benefits (ibid.).

Also, the issue of protection becomes more complicated when it is linked to the detention and deportation of foreigners. In fact, the states have a legal responsibility to protect survivors of gender-based violence (GBV) and to prevent violence against women (VAW). Factually, however, this doctrine is ambiguous when either the victim or the perpetrator lacks formal legal status. For example, an analysis of civil society protests in Canada against a 2011 directive allowing border guards to enter women’s shelters to deport unauthorized migrants distinguishes between two positions: statist appeals calling upon the government to protect all survivors regardless of immigration status, which promotes Northern governments as protectors of vulnerable women and of gender equality, concealing structural inequalities such as birthright citizenship and perceived North-South differences in gender norms. And state-critical framings that portray the state as perpetrator and accomplice of individual perpetrators of VAW, especially in the context of immigration enforcement (Abji 2016). Further deconstructing the notion of the state as protector of human and women’s rights is the analysis

of US immigration raids as “racialised spectacle meant to legitimate a masculinised state authority” (Sampaio 2014). In a similar vein, the role of states and interstate relations in creating an environment for trafficking-like situations, deportability and expendability/disposability especially for women has received attention in research on labour mobility to Gulf states (Mahdavi 2011). Countering the “moral panic” about humans, and specifically sex trafficking of individuals believed to have been tricked into making a bad decision, this study draws attention to the key role of sending and receiving states (Mahdavi 2011). While the Kafala or sponsorship system (requiring labour migrants in Dubai and the UAE to have a citizen sponsor) creates unique forms of dependence and legal vulnerability, states around the world share interests in maintaining remittance flows or filling gaps in the intimate and care sectors.

Post return

A study on assisted return from Germany finds that, especially, economic reintegration is more challenging to achieve for women, particularly reintegration into the formal labor market, which is attributed to weaker or different networks, family and care obligations, gender norms and lower acquisition of transferable skills and resources during migration (Hussain, Coskun, & Clevers 2025). Research in the context of assisted return and reintegration, however, is more likely to attribute reintegration challenges to violence experienced due to unsafe migration channels or to gendered norms restricting women in the origin country than to violence encountered during asylum processing, detention or return (IOM studies, e.g., 2021). A study on the social ramifications of deportations (women deported from the EU to Nigeria) looks at deportation not only as radical non-belonging, but as embedded in and impacting on social relationships (Ratia & Notermans, 2012). It finds that internalized beliefs about the links between geographical and social mobility drive migration aspirations as well as return experiences, with empty-handed return being stigmatized. Stigma, according to this analysis, is attached to the failure to meet migration goals, not to sex work, as returning sex workers are respected by many when they return with money (ibid.). Despite isolation, legal insecurity and unsafe working conditions, none of the respondents wanted to or felt relieved about their forced return. This research adds an additional aspect, namely the classed (and gendered) dimension of the return stigma. According to one respondent, “the social stigma is about rich people laughing at poor people who try to make something of themselves and fail” (ibid.). The authors furthermore note that most women were confronted by their family for coming back with nothing, but none of the men were (ibid.).

Lastly, a very understudied topic is return policy frameworks of origin countries. Only one paper in the entire sample undertakes an intersectionality-based policy analysis of Mexico’s return policies (Fernández-Sánchez et al. 2023). Findings from this study are that binary understandings of male female and voluntary vs deported (disregarding that many people decide to return under enormous pressure) prevail. Main gaps are a lack of attention to health care, failure to address the diversity of return migrants’ non-inclusion of families and communities of the returning migrants (Fernández-Sánchez et al. 2023).

5. Conclusion

This concept note has mapped conceptual, methodological, and empirical gaps in the literature on gender and return migration, with a particular focus on state-induced and coerced forms of return. By systematically reviewing and clustering existing research, it has been demonstrated that, while gender has gained visibility as a category of analysis in return studies, its treatment remains uneven, fragmented, and often insufficiently theorised. The literature reveals contradictory findings and partial insights that can only be understood in light of underlying conceptual tensions, methodological limitations, and selective perspectives in knowledge production.

A central conclusion is that gender is mobilized in markedly different ways across strands of literature. Research on assisted return and reintegration tends to rely on place-based and relatively static understandings of gender norms, often framing women as disadvantaged returnees facing culturally rooted constraints. In contrast, studies on bordering, detention, and migration control conceptualize gender as enacted, ascribed, and instrumentalized within power-laden practices of governance. These latter approaches offer more nuanced insights into how gender intersects with race, legal status, and class in producing deportability, immobilization, and differential exposure to violence. However, they remain weakly connected to post-return research, resulting in fragmented analyses that obscure the cumulative and long-term effects of coerced mobility regimes.

Across the reviewed literature, significant gaps persist. Empirical research on return enforcement practices, particularly decision-making around assisted return, detention, and deportation, remains scarce due to limited access and ethical challenges. Reintegration assistance is more frequently studied, yet often in depoliticized ways that foreground individual deficits while neglecting the gendered power relations embedded in programme design and implementation. Quantitative and comparative research is strikingly limited, and data collection practices frequently reproduce binary and cisnormative assumptions, thereby excluding diverse gender identities and intersectional experiences. Reflexivity regarding researcher positionality and the gendered dynamics of data collection is rarely addressed, despite the sensitivity and stigma surrounding return experiences.

The review further highlights pronounced gaps in perspective. Research continues to privilege receiving-state viewpoints, while the voices of origin societies, families, and non-migrants at return locations remain marginal. This imbalance constrains understanding of how return is socially negotiated, stigmatized, or normalized beyond the individual returnee. Similarly, South–South returns and origin-country return policies are mainly absent from the literature, limiting insights into global inequalities and the transnational governance of return.

Taken together, these findings underscore that the key challenge is not whether gender is included in analyses of return migration, but how it is conceptualized, operationalized, and politicized. Gender-responsive return governance cannot be reduced to identifying vulnerable groups or to the formal mainstreaming of gender into policy frameworks. Instead, it requires sustained attention to intersectionality, structural inequalities, and the conflicting logics between migration control and protection. Future research would benefit from longitudinal, comparative, and gender-responsive methodologies that connect pre-return experiences, enforcement practices, and post-return trajectories, while centering care relations, agency, and accountability. Only through such integrated and reflexive approaches can scholarship meaningfully contribute to more equitable and just return policies and practices.

References

- Aberman, Tanya (2022): Forced-voluntary return. In: *Migration and Society* 5 (1), 13–28. DOI: 10.3167/arms.2022.050103.
- Abji, Salina (2016): ‘Because Deportation is Violence Against Women’: On the Politics of State Responsibility and Women’s Human Rights. In: *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society* 23 (4), 483–507. DOI: 10.1093/sp/jxw004.
- Ashutosh, Ishan, and Mountz, Alison (2011): Migration management for the benefit of whom? Interrogating the work of the International Organization for Migration. In: *Citizenship Studies* 15 (1), 21–38. DOI: 10.1080/13621025.2011.534914.
- Askola, Heli (2010): ‘Illegal migrants’, gender and vulnerability: The case of the EU’s returns directive. In: *Feminist Legal Studies* 18 (2), 159–178. DOI: 10.1007/s10691-010-9153-2.
- Baker, Beth, and Marchevsky, Alejandra (2019): Gendering deportation, policy violence, and Latino/a family precarity. In: *Latino Studies* 17 (2), 207–224. DOI: 10.1057/s41276-019-00176-0.
- Belknap, Ruth A. (2016): Desert, detention, and deportation: Mexican women's descriptions of migration stressors and sources of strength. In: *Health Care for Women International* 37 (9), 995–1009. DOI: 10.1080/07399332.2016.1162165.
- Black, Richard; Koser, Khalid; Munk, Karen; Atfield, Gaby; D’Onofrio, Lisa, and Tiemoko, Richmond (2004): *Understanding Voluntary Return*. Home Office Online Report 50/04, Sussex: Home Office.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242490813_Understanding_Voluntary_Return.
- Bosworth, Mary; Fili, Andriani, and Pickering, Sharon (2018): Women and border policing at the edges of Europe. In: *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 44 (13), 2182–2196. DOI: 10.1080/1369183X.2017.1408459.
- Celorio, Rosa; Ellsberg, Mary; Sandoval, Carolina J., and Nassif, Gabriella (2025): Gendered Consequences of U.S. Mass Deportations: How Shifting Migration Policies Endanger Women and Girls. In: *Georgetown Journal of International Affairs*.
- Cleton, Laura, and Meier, Petra (2023): Contesting policy categories using intersectionality: reflections for studying migration governance. In: *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 46 (14), 3014–3036. DOI: 10.1080/01419870.2023.2171737.
- Cornwall, Andrea, and Rivas, Althea-Maria (2015): From ‘gender equality and ‘women’s empowerment’ to global justice: reclaiming a transformative agenda for gender and development. In: *Third World Quarterly* 36 (2), 396–415. DOI: 10.1080/01436597.2015.1013341.
- Crawley, Heaven, and Lester, Trine (2004): *Comparative analysis of gender-related persecution in national asylum legislation and practice in Europe*. Geneva: UNHCR. <https://pureportal.coventry.ac.uk/en/publications/comparative-analysis-of-gender-related-persecution-in-national-as/>.
- Dahinden, Janine (2010): Are you who you know? A network perspective on ethnicity, gender and transnationalism: Albanian-speaking migrants in Switzerland and returnees in Kosovo. In: Westin, Charles; Bastos, José; Dahinden, Janine, and Gois, Pedro (Eds.): *Identity Processes and Dynamics in Multi-Ethnic Europe*. IMISCOE Research, Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 127–147.
- Das Gupta, Monisha (2014): “Don’t Deport Our Daddies”. In: *Gender & Society* 28 (1), 83–109. DOI: 10.1177/0891243213508840.

- Donato, Stellamarina (2023): Women migrant returnees as intermediaries: Exploring empowerment and agency of migrant women returnees in the eu-mena region. In: *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 1–17. DOI: 10.1007/s12134-023-01095-9.
- Encinas, Monica (2016): Assisted Voluntary Return: implications for women and children. In: *forced migration review* (52), 84–86.
- Fernández-Sánchez, Higinio; Salma, Jordana; Dorow, Sara, and Salami, Bukola (2023): A multi-scalar critical analysis of return migration policies in Mexico. In: *International Migration* 61 (6), 175–192. DOI: 10.1111/imig.13157.
- Gerlach, Alice (2018): *Immigration Enforcement in the UK: How Women Experience Detention, Release and Removal*. University of Oxford, Oxford.
<https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:f50557b1-5328-4a25-b72e-23dbdoc5cf4d/files/mo4b0oco4b01369ce8f41f10oce4d98af>.
- Golash-Boza, Tanya, and Hondagneu-Sotelo, Pierrette (2013): Latino immigrant men and the deportation crisis: A gendered racial removal program. In: *Latino Studies* 11 (3), 271–292. DOI: 10.1057/lst.2013.14.
- Hansen, Peter (2008): Circumcising Migration: Gendering Return Migration among Somalilanders. In: *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 34 (7), 1109–1125. DOI: 10.1080/13691830802230422.
- Hennebry, Jenna L., and Petrozziello, Allison J. (2019): Closing the Gap? Gender and the Global Compacts for Migration and Refugees. In: *International Migration* 57 (6), 115–138. DOI: 10.1111/imig.12640.
- Hussain, Ayesha; Coskun, Laura, and Clevers, Franziska (2025): *Gendered Economic Reintegration of Return Migrants in Nigeria and Iraq. Further Insights from StarthilfePlus*. Berlin: IOM.
- International Organization for Migration (2023): *Gendered Reintegration Experiences and Gender-Sensitive/Responsive/Transformative Approaches to Reintegration Assistance*. Geneva: IOM.
https://migrantprotection.iom.int/system/files/resources/8eef7a94-6071-4d0b-bf88-eeedcbfc3b6b/document/Final%20version_BMZ%20gender%20study.pdf?type=node&id=5156&lang=en.
- King, Russel, and Lulle, Anja (2022): Gendering return migration. In: King, Russel, and Kuschminder, Katie (Eds.): *Handbook of return migration*. Elgar handbooks in migration series, Cheltenham, UK, Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar Publishing, 53–69.
- Koch, Anne (2014): The Politics and Discourse of Migrant Return: The Role of UNHCR and IOM in the Governance of Return. In: *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 40 (6), 905–923. DOI: 10.1080/1369183X.2013.855073.
- Krause, Ulrike (2024): Invisibilization of the unwanted Others? Feminist, queer, and postcolonial perspectives on the 1951 Refugee Convention’s drafting. In: *Women's Studies International Forum* 107, 102979. DOI: 10.1016/j.wsif.2024.102979.
- Lewis, Rachel A. (2014): “Gay? Prove it”: The politics of queer anti-deportation activism. In: *Sexualities* 17 (8), 958–975. DOI: 10.1177/1363460714552253.
- Lochan, Annalisa (2017): The Effects of Assisted Voluntary Return Programs on Marginalized Women: A Critique of the IOM and UNHCR. In: *Laurier Undergraduate Journal of the Arts* 4 (1). <https://scholars.wlu.ca/luja/vol4/iss1/5>.

- Mahdavi, Pardis (2011): "But we can always get more!". *Deportability, the State and Gendered Migration in the United Arab Emirates*. In: *Asian and Pacific Migration Journal* 20 (3-4), 413–431.
- Mahon, Rianne (2020): *Gendering migration management*. In: *The International Organization for Migration*, 53–73. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-32976-1_3.
- Matos, R., and Esposito, F. (2019): *Women's experiences of border crossing: gender, mobility and border control*. In: *International Journal of Migration and Border Studies*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Women%27s-experiences-of-border-crossing%3A-gender%2C-and-Matos-Esposito/ed002661d6fab3235acaba63650c90983bc7c558>.
- Milivojević, Sanja (2018): *Race, Gender, and Border Control in the Western Balkans*. Bd. 1. Oxford University Press. DOI: 10.1093/oso/9780198814887.003.0006.
- Paasche, Erlend, and Skilbrei, May-Len (2017): *Gendered vulnerability and return migration*. In: *Temida* 20 (2), 149–166. DOI: 10.2298/TEM1702149P.
- Pickering, S., and Ham, J. (2014): *Hot Pants at the Border: Sorting Sex Work from Trafficking*. In: *The British Journal of Criminology* 54 (1), 2–19. DOI: 10.1093/bjc/azt060.
- Pinkow-Läpple, Janine I. (2023): 'That's so sexist!' How highly skilled female return migrants try to shape gender norms in Kosovo. In: *Central and Eastern European Migration Review* online first, 1–17. DOI: 10.54667/ceemr.2023.05.
- Rabin, Nina (2009): *Unseen Prisoners: A Report on Women in Immigration Detention Facilities in Arizona*.
- Ratia, Emma, and Notermans, Catrien (2012): "I was crying, I did not come back with anything": Women's experiences of deportation from Europe to Nigeria. In: *African Diaspora* 5 (2), 143–164. DOI: 10.1163/18725457-12341235.
- Sacchetti, Sandra (2016): *Assisted "voluntary" return of women to Kosovo. Rhetoric and reality within the framework of development*. In: *Regions and Cohesion* 6 (2), 35–58. DOI: 10.3167/reco.2016.060204.
- Sahin-Mencutek, Zeynep, and Triandafyllidou, Anna (2024): *Coerced return: formal policies, informal practices and migrants' navigation*. In: *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/1369183X.2024.2371209.
- Şahin-Mencütek, Zeynep (2024): *Conceptual Complexity About Return Migration of Refugees/Asylum Seekers*. In: *Journal of Asian and African Studies* 59 (7), 2125–2138. DOI: 10.1177/00219096241283651.
- Sahraoui, Nina (2020): *Gendering the care/control nexus of the humanitarian border: Women's bodies and gendered control of mobility in a European borderland*. In: *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space* 38 (5), 905–922. DOI: 10.1177/0263775820925487.
- Sampaio, Anna (2014): *Racing and gendering immigration politics: analyzing contemporary immigration enforcement using intersectional analysis*. In: *Politics, Groups, and Identities* 2 (2), 202–221. DOI: 10.1080/21565503.2014.909319.
- Spijkerboer, Thomas (2017): *Gender and Refugee Status*. London: Routledge. DOI: 10.4324/9781315254692.
- Strijbosch, Karlien; Mazzucato, Valentina, and Brunotte, Ulrike (2023): *Performing return: victims, criminals or heroes? Senegalese male returnees engaging with the stigma of deportation*. In: *Gender, Place & Culture* 30 (11), 1617–1637. DOI: 10.1080/0966369X.2023.2229056.

- Szekely, Dorottya (2024): Four reasons why we need gender mainstreaming in migration data.
- Vlase, Ionela (2013): 'My Husband Is a Patriot!': Gender and Romanian Family Return Migration from Italy. In: *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 39 (5), 741–758. DOI: 10.1080/1369183X.2013.756661.
- Vogler, Stefan, and Rosales, Rocío (2023): Classification and Coercion: The Gendered Punishment of Transgender Women in Immigration Detention. In: *Social Problems* 70 (3), 698–716. DOI: 10.1093/socpro/spac022.
- Vollmer, Ruth, and Schmitz-Pranghe, Clara (2025): Inside the Black Box: Tracing Interactions Between Stratified Reintegration Trajectories and Street-Level Implementation of Reintegration Assistance. In: *International Migration* 63 (4), Artikel e70061. DOI: 10.1111/imig.70061.
- Wadia, Khursheed (2015): Regimes of insecurity: Women and immigration detention in France and Britain. In: *The Securitisation of Migration in the EU*, 91–118. DOI: 10.1057/9781137480583_5.
- Warner, Avery E. (2025): Crimmigration and the punishment of women: Evidence from Texas courts. In: *Social Science Research* 128, 103163. DOI: 10.1016/j.ssresearch.2025.103163.
- Wissink, Lieke M. (2021): Making populations for deportation: Bureaucratic knowledge practices inside a European deportation unit. In: *PoLAR: Political and Legal Anthropology Review* 44 (2), 256–270. DOI: 10.1111/plar.12447.

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